

The HuT

Template for documenting DRR solutions and the transfer process

Deliverable D5.2

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP5 Transferability and scalability, T5.1 Overview of existing knowledge

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1. Technical references

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- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
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1.1. Document history

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3. Amplifying process in The HuT

Following the state-of-the-art analysis for transfer and scaling of DRR solution/innovation, and detailed comparison of processes in The Hut, the amplifying framework was provided in D5.1 (Smetanova et al, 2023). Hereby, the basic description of the main terms and processes is given.

1. **Amplifying within** - extending impact within the demonstrator, where the solution / innovation originated. It has two subprocesses:
 - 1.1 Stabilizing – the process of strengthening the structures, linkages, connections which support the existence/sustaining of a solution/innovation.
 - 1.2 Speeding up – the process of accelerating the impact of the solution/innovation in the demonstrator.

Figure 1: The HuT Amplifying framework (Deliverable 5.1, modified after Lamm et al, 2020)

2. **Amplifying out** – increasing the impact range of the solution/innovation outside of its original context.
 - 2.1 Growing – the process of doing the same solution/innovation in a similar context.
 - 2.2 Replicating – the process of doing the same solution/innovation in dissimilar context.
 - 2.3 Transferring – the process of doing a similar (independent of original) solution/innovation in a context similar to the context of the original solution/innovation. Please refer to this category solely: Amplifying out/Transferring, to avoid confusion with the verbs “transfer” and “transferring”.

- 2.4 Spreading – the process of doing a similar (independent or original) solution /innovation in a context dissimilar to the context of the original solution /innovation.
3. **Amplifying beyond** – processes changing the system components and linkages, which influence (enable or hinder) the solution's/innovation's impact.
- 3.1 Scaling up – the process of increasing impact via reaching higher institutional levels and embedding the solution/ innovation into operational schemes or policies.
- 3.2 Scaling deep – processes of changing the values, perceptions and habits influencing the solution/innovation's impact.
- 3.3. Scaling down – the process of ensuring that changes in laws, policies or norms, have the necessary means to implement the envisaged good practices on the ground (Rodriguez et al. 2020; RECONNECT framework)

Each **amplifying process** of DRR- solution/innovation **has the main outcome**, which describe **overarching goal** of amplifying **at the end of the project**. Amplifying can have one final **tangible output** at the end of the project or multiple tangible outputs during the project. **Impact of amplifying process** is a long-term change which is envisaged by amplifying of a DRR- solution/innovation (measurable in 3-5 few years) after the project end.

3.1. The HuT amplifying stories

In September 2023 we conducted semi-structured interviews with the ten demonstrators. Firstly, the amplifying framework (Deliverable 5.1) was explained. Secondly, the partners were asked to describe the DRR- solution/innovation and related activities, which they were working on. The authors of the report helped to identify the amplifying process related to these activities and project tasks. We refer to the activities match into an amplifying process as an “amplifying story”. The majority of the demonstrators work on multiple activities and project tasks. Those activities/tasks lead to the solution/innovation amplifying. The activities/tasks can be divided into three major amplifying processes – amplifying within, amplifying out and amplifying beyond (Figure 2). Therefore, demonstrators are directly supporting The HuT amplifying while executing their activities within The HuT project. The monitoring of the amplifying process directly supports progress monitoring toward the self-defined goal of the solution/innovation development. The amplifying process monitoring is a supportive tool for demonstrators and all partners to monitor their progress.

There are multiple tasks in The HuT project, which support amplifying within the project. The Field Visit within task 5.2 is an example. The demonstrators and partners established a working group, which activities could be also explored as a mean to amplifying out. For the purpose of this deliverable, we will report to the demonstrators or partners who (through their existing/ planned activities) contribute to amplifying the DRR solution/innovation as “process owners”.

3.2. Advantages of monitoring and re-evaluation for demonstrators

It is important to note that amplifying activities are part of process owners' activities within the project. Framing of the activities as one amplifying process with a given outcome, output(s) can support a clear vision and navigate the process. Furthermore, such framing supports establishing of plan

for how to achieve the outcomes. Setting the steps leading to concrete outputs in a realistic timescale can help to navigate and monitor the activities.

Continuous monitoring of the amplifying process (which is based in existing activities) provides a mirror to the functioning of selected approaches. Monitoring serves as a “witness” of amplifying processes, showing how far we have moved since the beginning. Similar approach is used in coaching and supervision practice and is especially helpful in processes where progress is slow and without obvious measurable results. Such approach is also recommendable when the participants tend to dwell deep into the process, and it is difficult to assess the progress and continuation with a distance.

Amplifying mosaic within The HuT

Figure 2: Mosaic of the demonstrator activities across the amplifying framework (status, Oct 2023); specifically, only the most relevant amplifying process will be selected and monitored in each DEM.

Continuous process noting and assessment assist to remember the events as they happened. They help to better analyse necessity of adjustment, and to look for specific questions and solution when seeking the adjustment. It is also possible to set performance indicators as additional monitoring tool. In that case, process owner could report the progress towards an indicator on regular basis. Both methods support evaluating, recognizing, acknowledging, and celebrating the success of the process.

Simple stepwise monitoring can help the process owner to summarize the progress and communicate it to The HuT partners. Monitoring allows early identifying when need for assistance or support might be needed. Performance indicators of an amplifying process could be directly linked to The HuT key performance indicators. In this way the process owners’ contribution to project success can be directly seen.

Additionally, the monitoring and evaluation of the amplifying process collect evidence for analysis, which will potentially translate into the deliverable 5.5 “Amplifying Roadmap”, the overall project goals, and ultimately advance the knowledge and best practice of DRR solution/innovation amplifying (transfer and scaling).

4. Template to document amplifying of DRR solution/innovation

Standardized approach for monitoring of amplifying processes is developed for The HuT. The data collection for monitoring is done through the template introduced in this chapter. The template serves two purposes – monitoring and evaluation, and support of demonstrators to reflect on the progress in their amplifying process.

Each **process** owner will **report one amplifying story** to be able to monitor the amplifying process the process owner needs to **set clear outcomes of the amplifying process**. For each story outputs and progress indicators can be set.

The template is based on reporting the **main interactions** related to the activities representing the amplifying process. We use the word interaction to refer to any important step in the activities leading to amplifying. This can be any type of meetings (e.g., with stakeholder, partners, one-to-one, group workshop, information meeting, or capacity building meetings, ...), advancement of the innovation (e.g., setting up monitoring sensors, finalizing concept for model integration, science-art event, feedback collecting via survey...). The interaction which are reported shall be relevant for the process. We especially encourage to report the relevant interaction independently of being successful. We encourage to report interaction of all three kinds: (i) successful, (ii) not successful, and (iii) “neutral” interactions. In this way we can learn more about the enablers and barriers of innovation transfer process.

Template consists of **11 required** and 4 optional **questions** (Table 1). There are questions related to type of interaction (Question 1), description of the interaction and situation before, during and after (questions 2, 4, 5, 6), questions related to duration (question 7), personnel involvement (question 3), contribution to outcome (questions 8 and 9), enablers (question 10) and barriers (questions 11). Optional are questions about outputs, contribution to progress indicators, and additional comments (questions 12-15). Each process owner will have separate template for their amplifying story, therefore type of process is not asked. Data are of different type (Table 1) and will be analysed by mixed methods.

Data will be collected quarterly using the existing data collection tool of The HuT - the LogBook. Each process owner will find a unique link to a Excel table with a template, which they shall fill in. Each process owner will **report one amplifying story**. The amplifying story will be discussed with the authors of this report **prior to the onset of monitoring. The questionnaire will be adjusted for each process owner**. For example, with the support of the authors of the report, it will be clearly defined what is the aim and outcome of the process. The main interaction categories involved people will be agreed on. Process owners will be asked to **describe a minimum of one relevant interaction per quarter**. If the process owner wishes to report more than one interaction, they can easily fill in as many rows as they wish.

The template was compared for synergies and complementarity with existing HuT templates (as of September 2023) Selected questions do not double information already collected in the consortium. The demonstrators and partners tested the questionnaire during the General Assembly. All comments have been considered. Though previously planned, the results confirmed the inevitability of support in the pre-selection of amplifying story, identifying the outcomes, and tailoring of monitoring template for each process owner. Therefore, those will be part of the further steps before setting the monitoring via template in practice. The survey is then aimed at monitoring the advancements at a quarterly scale within a well-defined amplifying

process; it is expected that in some months multiple activities could be reported while, due to the unavoidable bottlenecks, in other months minimum progresses will be achieved.

Table 1: Template questionnaire

	Question	Type	Instruction
1	Type of interaction	Category	Selection from drop list
2	Describe the interaction in brief	Text	Give a short title (max 15 words)
3	Who was involved ?	Category	Multiple selection (incl. internal staff)
4	Describe the situation (in the amplifying) before this interaction happened?	Text	Describe (max 300 words)
5	What happened during the interaction?	Text	Describe (max 300 words)
6	Describe the situation (in the amplifying) after this interaction?	Text	Describe (max 300 words)
7	How many hours your team together approximately needed to prepare, implement and de-brief the interaction?	Numerical	Prepare – add number Implement – add number De-brief – add number
8	I assess the contribution to defined (amplifying process) outcome as...	Ordinary	Select: 1 very contributive, 2 rather contributive, 3 rather not contributive, 4 not contributive
9	Explain your answer in previous question	Text	Describe (max 500 words)
10	Name one thing which worked well, and you want to use it in further process	Text	Describe (max 30 words)
11	Name one thing which did not worked. If you know how, suggest how you could improve it in the further process	Text	Describe (max 30 words) If you do not know how to improve, please mention it.
12	Type of output related to interaction (if it was pre-defined) .	Category	Select from predefined categories Optional
13	Only if output was selected Describe the tangible output	Text	Describe (max 30 words) Optional
14	If you set a progress indicator for the amplifying process. How many percent of its target value have you reached through this interaction?	Number (%)	Optional
15	Anything else you want to add?	Text	Describe (max 500 words) You can share the needs for support, commentaries to the questionnaire.

4.1. Process owners will be supported in the monitoring process

The authors of the report and WP5 will support the process owners. We will **support selection of amplifying stories to report**. We help to **identify process outcomes, output(s)**. We will **discuss the main steps of the process, the most frequent interactions** which may appear, **categories of people involved**, and other categorical data which will become the section list in the tailored template. If there will be interest, we will support setting of the progress indicators.

Before the reporting deadline (set by LogBook reporting) process owners will be **offered support in filling the questionnaire** (during one-to-one interview). The reporting period for which the interaction shall be reported will be explicitly written in the LogBook. The process owners **will fill only what is relevant to them**. The process owners will have access to the analysed results after several reports. The collected data will be accessible to all partners of The HuT in the internal survey folder. The consortium data protection and reuse rules will be applied. WP5 reserves the right to report on the amplifying process in an anonymized way outside of The HuT. If a non-anonymous way of presentation is necessary WP5 will ask the process owner for permission. If the process owner wishes to be presented in a non-anonymous way, they shall inform WP5. Template to document the amplifying process.

5. Conclusions

The template for documenting the amplifying process is provided to monitor and evaluate the amplifying processes within The HuT amplifying framework (deliverable 5.1). Demonstrators and partners taking part in amplifying (process owners) were supported to define the amplifying processes they contribute to through their activities in the project. Process owners are further supported by WP5 to define the outcomes of the amplifying process and clarify the steps. This cooperation will help to tailor the template for each process owner to report on relevant issues. The amplifying process will be reported within existing LogBook reporting. The information collected will support the understanding of the progress in amplifying on demonstrator and project level. Furthermore, it is thought to support the understanding of the interaction the amplifying process consists of, the bottlenecks and enablers which experts face while amplifying DRR innovation/solutions.

6. References

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